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Love's Labour's Lost?: Locating Love, Labour, and Capitalism in Asha Jaoar Majhe

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Abstract

This research paper attempts to show how the Bengali film *Asha Jaoar Majhe* (2014) displays the struggles of an unnamed couple in the complex web of corporate culture in Kolkata. Exploring the cinematic tools and techniques, the paper investigates how the film, also titled in English as *Labour of Love*, posits the notions of love and labour in the circumstances of the capitalist corporate system. In this paper, the intricacies of the interaction among love, labour, and the corporate culture will be explored to inform how these underlying connections constantly influence each other maintaining the exercise of power and control over the domestic spaces of the individuals. The paper also aims to establish how the 'Man' and the 'Woman' in the film are an archetype of all such couples stuck in the pattern of a corporate culture and how their ways of living, in almost every aspect, are bound to an endless cycle of domestic works and corporate pressures. Using theories of capitalism, psychoanalysis, and visual analysis, the paper finally investigates how the hardships of both the domestic and the corporate spaces are overcome by schizophrenic imagination and how that fantastic imagination fills up the void in the lives of the couple which is created by the rat race of the corporate culture. By studying the nuances and details of the cinematic visuals, the paper also intends to capture the onomatopoeic implications that suggest of the apparent corporate setting of the film.

Keywords: Love, labour, capitalism, corporate culture, Asha Jaoar Majhe.

Introduction

Asha Jaoar Majhe, which is also known as *Labour of Love*, is an Indian film directed by Aditya Vikram Sengupta. The film is a "lyrical masterpiece" throwing light on the lifestyle of an employed couple.

The film has no dialogue, yet the truth and struggle of life are loud enough to prick the minds of the spectators. The capitalist society has situated the couple in such a position that they have hardly any time left for love and life. A profound message is lurking in the very silence of the film. The film's title translates into "in-between coming and going" which implies the liminal living of the couple. This liminality is a capitalist product resulting from the ambivalence of compulsive living under corporate rules. The official English title of the film, *Labour of Love* is no less important in this context because of its direct signification to a Marxian outlet of the film.

This paper attempts to study the film by exploring the cinematic tools and techniques employed by the director-writer. By studying the cinematic visuals, codes, sounds, and other elements encoded in the film, the paper brings the visual and onomatopoeic significations to the fore. In the film, the Man and the Woman are symbolic of working-class couples who are, in Marxian terms, "proletariat", and the society in which they have been situated is indicative of a capitalist structure run by the "bourgeoisie". Marx and Engels write in *The Communist Manifesto*:

The modern bourgeois society that has sprouted from the ruins of feudal society has not done away with class antagonisms. It has but established new classes, new conditions of oppression, new forms of struggle in place of the old ones... it has

simplified the class antagonisms: Society as a whole is more and more splitting up into two great hostile camps: Bourgeoisie and Proletariat (25).

This paper involves discussion with this complex capitalist structure of society in connection to the notions of love and labour. This paper will analyse the audio-visual codes of the film based on the general theories of capitalism, psychoanalysis, and visual analysis. The theory of capitalism will be employed to understand the politics behind the position of this working-class couple in the conditions of corporate spaces that entrap them in helpless opposite shifts. The theory of psychoanalysis will be used to decipher the impact of the corporate culture on the emotional and psychological states of the couple and their schizophrenic attempts to escape from the real world to an alternative imaginary one where life is exactly what they want it to be. The visual analysis will aid in decoding and deconstructing the film thoroughly.

The film, set in the backdrop of the topsy-turvy urban milieu of Calcutta, is a poetic tale that unfolds the lives of two ordinary persons caught up in the rat trap of a corporate culture. Their lifestyles are bound to an endless cycle of domestic works which seems predetermined by a deep sense of mutuality and understanding. One continuing the discontinued domestic work left by the other in the hurry of the pressure of a corporate job is the silent slap that the film inflicts upon the face of the capitalist society. Their love language is limited to the mutual domestic work and in the long waiting for each other. In their earnest waiting for each other's arrival, they wait for that crucial moment in the morning when they come across each other for a very brief time. The moment becomes an eternity where they dream of a perfect life walking around the woods in a very romantic setting. Full of politically woven underpinnings, this great poetic art of Aditya Vikram Sengupta speaks volume of incomplete wishes and oppressed desires of a married couple which are borne out of the obstructions and challenges posed by the compulsive time-tables of corporate culture (Sengupta).

In the film, Ritwick Chakraborty played the role of "the Man" and Basabdatta Chatterjee 'the Woman'.

The characters are kept anonymous so as to give a universal identity to the couple who are caught in the corporate system of the society. The focal points of the film might be the faces of these two characters in both the contexts of the domestic and the corporate, but the issues raised can be placed in a larger picture of contemporary situations. The Man works in a printing press, and the Woman works in a handbag-producing company. This is a tragic story where the owners who hold the means of production are in a way controlling the lifestyle of a working-class couple. In this respect, Marx and Engels write that "not only are they slaves of the bourgeois class, and of the bourgeois State; they are daily and hourly enslaved by the machine, by the overlooker, and, above all, by the individual bourgeois manufacturer himself" (30). Thus, this working-class couple is historically subject to the injustices and inhumanities of the factories and other institutions which perpetuate the age-old customs of enslavement and subjection.

The very beginning of the film, where a newsreader reports a chaotic situation of unemployment and its resultant issues in the then-contemporary scene in Kolkata, is symbolic of what the film is going to be about. The onomatopoeic significance of the background audio of the film underscores the presence of the growing capitalism. In the film, the daily drudgery of life has been expressed through the visuals and sounds of the printing press, stitching machines, bus routes, tram lines, complicated web of electric wires, television, structured buildings, and multiple narrow lanes. All these sounds and images imply the daily patterns of workers' lives who invest most of their lifetime in factories and corporate spaces for the fundamental needs of food and shelter. The silent language of the film suggests the silent sufferings of the unnamed couple. At the cruel hands of the capitalist systems of production, this working-class married couple lacks sufficient time for love and romance.

The encoded visuals that are presented in the film carry the obvious message of a capitalist turn of Indian societies and its vivid impact on the lives of people, particularly the working class. The transformation of an agrarian society into a full-fledged

capitalist society in India is an outcome of industrial revolutions that primarily emerged in the West and eventually in India. The emergence of industrialism and the resultant formation of capitalist social structures are more obvious in the massive (trans) formation of various institutional infrastructures after the independence of India. Had the transformation not happened in India, the working-class couple would have had sufficient time to spend with each other! But in a capitalist society where time is sold in return for money, free time is a rare thing to secure due to the compulsion of corporate rules and regulations. The socially realistic frames of the film speak volumes of the compulsive constraints of love in times of capitalism and its resultant crude corporate systems.

In between the film, although the film involves no dialogue and no language, it can be heard from the background that a protest procession is at work against unemployment and other working-class issues of the time. This announcement of protest presents a stark political contrast that underlines the socio-political upheavals of the time and the non-participation of the oppressed couple in the then-social structure. This voluntary move of this working-class couple being a-political in the case of such a political crisis can be equated with a silent yet sounding protest that the film strikes at. This shows the utter helplessness of the working-class life which does have rarely any spare time left for protest or revolution. The couple constantly suffers from a corporate culture full of capitalist ideals. Consequently, they end up being in a vicious cycle that echoes the daily struggles and attempts to have a handful of peace and quality time with the ones they love. For the sustenance of life, love is, of course, a requirement, but it is not the only thing that leads to a complete living in a capitalist society. Fundamental needs of living include a range of things including food, shelter, clothes, etc. So, the means to leading a so-called 'complete life' do not come free in a society which is entirely engulfed in the materialist interests of the corporate society. In this respect, Raju J. Das writes in his book *Contradictions of capitalist society and culture*, "Love in the wider sense requires socialism/communism. It is as well a part of the process of fighting for communism" (65).

The film depicts a social reality that speaks for the people who are stuck in a vicious cycle of work life. This married couple found a way to dodge the reality by adapting to its repetitive 'coming and going'. They engage in a different kind of love by sharing each other's domestic duties even under the compulsive constraints of love in times of capitalism and its resultant crude corporate systems. They invest themselves in preparing food, and washing dishes and dresses. Iteration of this same routine on a daily basis is the love language they share with each other. The lack of sufficient time for their physical proximity leads them to a higher kind of love that transcends the strictures of time and space in the oppressive corporate society. This lack of physical intimacy due to constraints of spare time leads to a different kind of psychological fulfilment through alternative means of imagination and schizophrenia.

The realistic environment that the film builds on from the beginning does, in no way, inform the audience that the characters will suffer a psychotic metamorphosis at the end of the film. The whole film is focused on the everyday patterns of their mutual domestic works and the patient waiting for that fleeting moment of joy in the morning. In the long wait for each other's arrival, the couple can only spend a temporary crucial moment with each other in the morning when they come across each other. The fulfilment of the couple's rather metaphysical love is so well displayed by their schizophrenia which involves the reverie of walking in the woods and spending romantic moments in the jungle. The transformation of the premise of the home into a setting in an unhomely jungle with the installation of the homely bed is the height of schizophrenia symbolizing the dark situational irony. This reversal of the crude reality by the fantasy is the product of their silent psychological vengeance upon the system which has compelled them into such an unfulfilling lifestyle. A closer psychoanalysis of this particular scene may reveal how this unnamed universal couple silently protest against the busy schedules of corporate mills and factories.

Conclusion

This paper has attempted to delineate how the film is a silent critique of capitalism and its resulting impact on the individual and social life of working-class

people. The power and politics of the capitalist systems behind the position of this working-class couple in the context of corporate spaces are countered by the rebellion of the couple in an alternative space that is marked by imagination and schizophrenia. The short encounter between their "coming and going" is a time when their "labours of love" have come to fruition. This marks that *love's labour* is not *lost*. Even after the oppression of the capitalist social structure of the then-time, the couple obtained a kind of ironic victory over the system by exercising the power of imagination or the descent into schizophrenia. In both of the activities, a silent yet volcanic protest against the system is apparently visible. This time is the grey time between the 'asha' (coming) and 'jaoya' (going) of the lovers from the place of love to the place of work. This seems to be a liminal space where their love gets a schizophrenic constant. This transient time in between when the couple meets is the time when they must bid farewell to each other because of the so-called punctuality of time in the capitalist corporate culture. This fleeting moment of togetherness enchanted by the background music suggests the literal timelessness of the couple's love story. There seems to be duality of meanings of this psychological state- a temporary escape from the cruel reality and an underlying message that this is the perpetual cycle of life working-class

people have to undergo all of eternity. In a way, this escape is but a continuity of similar love stories in other spaces, in other times, as in now and in forever. The continuity that capitalist society must keep intact for the labour of the product instead of labour of love, or life.

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